

1 **Ellagic acid metabolism by human gut microbiota: Consistent observation of**
2 **three urolithin phenotypes in intervention trials, independent of food source,**
3 **age and health status.**

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15 **ABSTRACT:** Three phenotypes for urolithins production after ellagitannins and ellagic acid intake are
16 consistently observed in different human intervention trials. Subjects can be stratified into three
17 urolithin-producing groups. 'Phenotype A' produced only urolithin A conjugates, which included
18 between 25-80% of the volunteers in the different trials. 'Phenotype B' produced isourolithin A
19 and/or urolithin B in addition to urolithin A, this being the second relevant group (10-50%).
20 'Phenotype O' (5-25%) was that in which these urolithins were not detected. The three phenotypes
21 were observed independently of the volunteers' health status and demographic characteristics (age,
22 gender, BMI (Body Mass Index)) and of the amount or type of ellagitannin food source ingested
23 (walnuts and other nuts, strawberries, raspberries and other berries or pomegranates). Interestingly,
24 a higher percentage of phenotype B was observed in those volunteers with chronic illness (metabolic
25 syndrome or colorectal cancer) associated with gut microbial imbalance (dysbiosis). These urolithin
26 phenotypes could show differences in the human gut microbiota and should be considered in
27 intervention trials dealing with health benefits of ellagitannins or ellagic acid. Whether this
28 phenotypic variation could be a biomarker related to differential health benefits or illness
29 predisposition deserves further research.

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32 **KEYWORDS:** *Polyphenol, meta-analysis, metabolite, microbiota, interindividual variability.*

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34 INTRODUCTION

35 Ellagitannins and ellagic acid are polyphenols often underestimated in our diet. However, they can
36 play an important role in the health effects observed after the intake of different food products such
37 as pomegranates, nuts, some berries (raspberry, blackberry, strawberry, cloudberry, etc.), tea,
38 muscadine grapes, many tropical fruits, oak aged wines and medicinal plants. Ellagitannins and
39 ellagic acid are transformed by the gut microbiota to produce urolithins, bioavailable metabolites
40 that can exert anti-inflammatory and anticarcinogenic effects,¹⁻³ and can reach high concentrations in
41 both normal and tumor human colonic tissues.⁴ There is, however, a large interindividual variability
42 in these health effects. The gut microbial composition in healthy humans and also the gut
43 microbioma imbalance (dysbiosis), which is associated with different chronic illnesses, such as
44 inflammatory bowel diseases (colitis, Crohn's disease, etc.), colon cancer, metabolic syndrome,
45 obesity and cirrhosis could be behind the different polyphenol metabolic profile.⁴

46 Differences in urolithin production, both quantity and chemical type, could explain, at least partly,
47 the large variability in the health effects observed *in vivo*. Urolithin A (**1**) is the main metabolite
48 observed in human plasma and urine, where it mainly occurs as conjugate forms with glucuronic acid
49 (**4**) and/or sulfate. However, isourolithin A (**2**) and urolithin B (**3**) (**Figure 1**) conjugates are also
50 observed in some volunteers, while in others urolithins are not produced or are present below the
51 limit of detection.⁴ Therefore, it is important to evaluate whether these metabolic behaviors are
52 consistent in different human populations (gender, age, health status, racial background and
53 geographic location), and if they are produced after consumption of different ellagitannin-containing
54 foods.

55 Our aim was to evaluate the ellagitannin/ellagic acid bioconversion capacity of humans to
56 produce urolithins. For this purpose, we evaluated the metabolic behavior of three groups of healthy
57 volunteers by analyzing their urinary urolithin profiles after the intake of walnuts and pomegranate
58 extracts. In addition, we performed a small meta-analysis by re-examining the metabolic profiles

59 observed in previous studies with volunteers of different ages, gender, and health status including
60 some characterized by a gut dysbiosis.

61 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

62 **Chemicals.** Urolithins were chemically synthesized (Villapharma, Murcia, Spain), as described
63 elsewhere.⁴ Purity was higher than 95% in all tested compounds.

64

65 **Intervention studies and study products.** Three intervention studies were performed and were
66 in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration and approved by the Ethics Committee from CSIC
67 (Madrid, Spain) (**Table 1**). All volunteers gave their written informed consent prior to participation
68 and they had not taken antibiotics during four weeks before the trials. In the three intervention
69 trials, volunteers consumed their usual diet but avoided ellagitannin-containing food products during
70 the study and one week before starting.

71 In the first intervention study, healthy volunteers (n=20, 11 men and 9 women) aged between 21
72 and 55 years consumed 30 g walnuts (edible part)/d for 3 d. Walnuts were purchased in a local
73 supermarket. After the last intake, 24 h-urine samples were collected. Urinary volume was measured
74 and the samples were immediately stored at -20 °C.

75 In the second intervention study healthy volunteers (n = 20, 10 men and 10 women) aged
76 between 18 and 23 years ingested 4 capsules of pomegranate extract in a single intake (total dose
77 1.8 g extract). Urine samples were also collected for 24 h after the intake and were immediately
78 stored at -20 °C.

79 In the third trial, overweight healthy subjects (n = 49, 32 men, 17 women; BMI (Body Mass Index)
80 > 27 kg/m²) aged between 40 and 65 years ingested 2 daily capsules of pomegranate extract (0.9 g/d)
81 for 3 d. Urine samples were collected for 24 h after the last intake and the urine stored at -20 °C until
82 further analysis. In both interventions 2 and 3 capsules containing pomegranate extract were kindly
83 supplied by Laboratorios Admira S.L. (Alcantarilla, Murcia, Spain).

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85 **Extraction protocol of urolithin metabolites.** Urine and feces samples were processed as
86 previously reported.^{4,5}

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88 **LC-MS analysis.** Samples were analyzed by HPLC-DAD-ESI-MS/MS or UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS as
89 previously reported.⁴

90

91 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

92 We report here that human subjects can be consistently clustered within three phenotypes, i.e.
93 ‘phenotype A’, ‘phenotype B’ or ‘phenotype 0’ according to their different capacity for excreting
94 urolithins, independently of their demographic characteristics, health status or ellagitannin-
95 containing food product (**Table 1**). This has been observed in three dietary interventions in healthy
96 volunteers (present study) as well as after re-examining available data for urinary profiles from
97 previous studies.

98 Urolithins are mainly detected either as aglycones in feces or as Phase-II metabolites in systemic
99 organs or biological fluids (glucuronide or sulfate derivatives). Overall, urolithin A (**1**) is the main
100 metabolite produced in humans and previously identified as urinary biomarker after consumption of
101 ellagitannins/ellagic acid from different food products.⁶ In the present study (**Table 1**), interventions
102 1, 2 and 3 with healthy volunteers, some volunteers excreted only Urolithin-A metabolites
103 (phenotype A), while other subjects, in addition to Urolithin A (**1**), also excreted urolithin B (**3**) and
104 isourolithin A (**2**) showing a more complex urinary metabolite profile (phenotype B) (**Figure 2**).
105 Furthermore, a third group that did not excrete urolithins in urine was also identified (phenotype 0).
106 The same three phenotypes were observed after intake of walnuts (intervention 1) or pomegranate
107 extracts (interventions 2 and 3).

108 This observation prompted us to re-examine the excretion profiles observed in previous studies
109 that we had previously completed in our laboratory or in collaboration with other research groups,
110 as well as with data available from other published studies. These three phenotypes were also found

111 in intervention studies either with healthy volunteers or with those volunteers having some disease
112 situations, confirming that these three phenotypes are quite robust and consistent (**Table 1**). In
113 accordance with the three interventions described here, the three phenotypes were also observed
114 no matter the source of ellagitannins ingested and the amount of ellagic acid ingested. They were
115 identified after the intake of walnuts, pomegranate juice,⁷ pomegranate extracts,⁴ strawberries,^{8,9}
116 raspberries,^{9,10} cloudbberries,⁹ and unpeeled nuts.¹¹

117 In healthy volunteers as well as in those patients with illnesses that are not characterized by gut
118 dysbiosis (prostate cancer or benign hyperplasia) phenotype A was the main urinary profile (**Table 1**;
119 **Figure 3**). In this regard, phenotype A was also the most abundant profile in patients with chronic
120 obstructive pulmonary disease (age 60 ± 11) that consumed pomegranate juice for 5 weeks,¹²
121 although data were not available for quantitative re-examination of the urinary profiles (results not
122 shown). In contrast, the ratio between phenotype A and B changed in patients with illness associated
123 with gut dysbiosis such as metabolic syndrome or colorectal cancer where phenotype B gained
124 increasing relevance (**Table 1**; **Figure 3**). Age, gender, BMI and geographical location did not affect
125 urolithin urinary profiles (**Table 1**). We hypothesize that gut dysbiosis is the cause of the increase in
126 the abundance of Isourolithin-A and Urolithin-B (phenotype B) in the patients with colon cancer and
127 metabolic syndrome (**Table 1**). Therefore, an urolithin production test could be a useful biomarker to
128 monitor certain gut microbial imbalances, or to assess treatment efficacy.

129 Previous studies from other groups also showed the presence of these three phenotypes, which
130 were within the range shown here. For example, a previous study of the urinary urolithins produced
131 after the intake of raspberries by healthy volunteers (n= 10) showed that 70% were only Urolithin-A
132 excreters (phenotype A), 20% excreted in addition Isourolithin-A and Urolithin-B (phenotype B) and
133 10% were non excreters (phenotype 0).¹⁰ Interestingly, in spite of the relatively low number of
134 volunteers, the distribution of the three phenotypes was similar to that observed in the three trials
135 with healthy subjects shown here. A recent study¹³ has reported the presence of three urinary
136 urolithin excretion patterns after the intake of tropical highland blackberry juice by healthy

137 volunteers that is also consistent with our results. However, demographic characteristics (age,
138 gender, BMI) of volunteers were not described and the ratio between phenotypes A and B was closer
139 to that found in patients with gut dysbiosis than that observed in healthy subjects. In addition, in this
140 previous study, the correlation of the production of Urolithin B with that of Isourolithin A was not
141 described, as Isourolithin A was not analyzed.

142 Our results show that stratification of subjects according to their urolithin phenotype should be
143 considered in ellagitannin and ellagic acid intervention trials. Three consistent enterotypes, with
144 different gut microbiota communities, have been described in humans.¹⁴ In line with the trend
145 highlighted by a previous study,¹⁵ the challenge now is to investigate the correlation between these
146 enterotypes, the three urolithin phenotypes and the possible impact on human health.

147

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222 **Figure legends**

223 **Figure 1.** Urolithin metabolites observed after ellagitannins intake. Urolithin A (1); Isourolithin A (2);
224 Urolithin B (3); Urolithin A-glucuronide (4); Isourolithin A glucuronide (5); Urolithin B glucuronide (6).

225

226 **Figure 2.** Characteristic HPLC-UV chromatograms showing the main urolithins corresponding to the
227 three phenotypes found in urine samples of volunteers, after the intake of walnuts.

228

229 **Figure 3.** Mean distribution of the three phenotypes present in healthy subjects and patients without
230 dysbiosis (n = 137) as well as in those patients with illness associated to gut dysbiosis (metabolic
231 syndrome, n = 42; and colorectal cancer, n = 26).

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Table 1. Urolithin Urinary Phenotype Distribution in Different Human Trials.

Trial	Food (Quantity ingested, Total EA content after hydrolysis/d)	Analytical technique	N	Age	BMI (kg/m²)	Health Status	Phenotype A	Phenotype B	Phenotype O
Intervention 1 (this study)	Walnuts (30g/d, 162.8 mg total EA)	HPLC-DAD-ESI-IT-MS/MS	20 (10 men, 10 women)	21-55	23.8±2.3	Healthy	13 (65%)	4 (20%)	3 (15%)
Intervention 2 (this study)	Pomegranate extract (1.8 g, 220 mg total EA)	UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS	20 (10 men, 10 women)	18-23	20.5±2.1	Healthy	16 (80%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)
Intervention 3 (this study)	Pomegranate extract (0.9 g/d, 110 mg total EA)	UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS	49 (32 men, 17 women)	40-65	30.4±3.4	Healthy-overweight	30 (60%)	15 (30%)	4 (10%)
González-Sarrías et al. ⁷	Walnuts (35 g/d, 190 mg total EA), pomegranate juice (200 mL/d, 165.7 mg total EA)	HPLC-DAD-ESI-IT-MS/MS	28 (men)	56-90	27.7±3.6	Prostate cancer or benign prostate hyperplasia	17 (60%)	4 (15%)	7 (25%)
Truchado et al. ⁸	Strawberry(200 g fresh strawberries or the equivalent in puree, 150 mg total EA)	HPLC-DAD-ESI-IT-MS/MS	20 (8 men, 12 women)	25-30	Not available	Healthy	16 (80%)	3 (15%)	1 (5%)
Puuponen-Pimia et al. ⁹	Strawberry (100 g/d, 75 mg total EA) + raspberry (100 g/d, 147 mg total EA) + cloudberry (100 g/d)	HPLC-DAD-ESI-IT-MS/MS	20 (10 men, 10 women)	50-65	31.8±4.4	Metabolic syndrome	5 (25%)	10 (50%)	5 (25%)
Tulipani et al. ¹¹	Nuts (unpeeled), (30 g/d, 81.4 mg total EA) (15 g walnuts +7.5 g almonds+7.5 g hazelnuts)	HPLC-DAD/ESI-QqQ-MS/MS and HPLC-ESI-IT-MS	22 (13 men, 9 women)	31-63	31.0±2.9	Metabolic syndrome	11 (50%)	9 (41%)	2 (9%)
Núñez-Sánchez et al. ⁴	Pomegranate extract (0.9 g/d, 110 mg total EA)	UPLC-ESI-QTOF-MS	26 (14 men, 12 women)	52-89	28.9±3.9	Colorectal cancer	11 (42.3%)	11 (42.3%)	4 (15.4%)

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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